

Behavioural Modernity

Laura McLean, Goldsmiths, London

Abstract

Behavioural Modernity explores the changing politics of representation and ethics of care in curatorial practice, necessitated by an increasing blurring of boundaries between the human, the technological, and the planetary.

Behavioural Modernity is the first exhibition in a two-part program at Artistic Bokeh exploring changing politics of representation and ethics of care in curatorial practice, necessitated by an increasing blurring of boundaries between the human, the technological, and the planetary.

The emergence of the modern human can be traced to between 50,000 and 100,000 years ago, depending on accepted archeological evidence. Ochre engraved with patterns, and shell beads dating back 77,000 years, for instance, have been unearthed at Blombos Cave, South Africa. Such artefacts reflecting symbolically mediated behaviour and abstract thinking and others that shows signs of advanced problem solving and long-range planning abilities betray cognitive traits and practices that separated Homo sapiens from our ancestors.

During this evolutionary period, human universals - features of culture, society, language, behaviour and psyche from which there are no known exceptions - emerged, which led to the triumph of modern humans as Earth's dominant hominoid, and our spread across the planet.

The Tower of Babel, according to the Book of Genesis, was constructed by a humanity united by one language. Settling in Shinar, Mesopotamia after the Great Flood, the Babylonians sought to make a name for themselves through the building of a great tower reaching to the heavens.

And they began to build, and in the fourth week they made brick with fire, and the bricks served them for stone, and the clay with which they cemented them together was asphalt which comes out of the sea, and out of the fountains of water in the land of Shinar. - Book of Jubilees

The construction of this monument was confounded by God, who disrupted the Babylonians' work, scattering them across the globe and confusing their language, thus establishing the different language groups and cultures of the world.

Since the Cartesian Revolution of the 17th century, a dualistic metaphysics dividing nature and culture, human and object, mind and body, and self and other has dominated Western thinking. These anthropocentric divides have governed our worldview, and guided the development of classificatory schema which seek to categorise all life and matter on Earth.

Such schema, based on visible attributes, make themselves apparent in museums, which act pedagogically to reinforce the hierarchisation and subjugation of both the human and non-human.

The violence of the impulse to know and understand the world within this rationalist framework has been particularly clear in the displays of ethnographic museums, whose collections are largely drawn from colonising expeditions, such as James Cook's voyages across the Pacific Ocean. Within these museums, the other has been wholly captured, contained, and represented within a European Humanist paradigm.

Behavioural Modernity brings together the work of two artists with object mountings loaned by the nearby Museum für Völkerkunde (Museum of Ethnology), to explore strategies for the transgression of classificatory schemas and museological tropes of demarcation in contemporary artistic and curatorial practices.

Desert glass, formed in the great sand sea of the Sahara around 26 million years ago, is presented with an accompanying object label in English and Arabic as part of Emily Jones' ongoing project The Draining of the Mesopotamian Marshes of Iraq. The circumstances that led to the creation of this glass in the sands is uncertain, and the ambiguity of the glass's origins are reflected in a scientific text that fails or refuses to pin these objects down.

Similarly presented is resin from *Callitris Endlicheri*, or Black Cyprus Pine, one of the Various Relics of a Bright Future by Clare Milledge. These include lumps of coal, and artefacts crafted from others materials of the Australian landscape: a sash jingling with bottle tops, a robe armoured with Elliot traps. Two masks offer the temporary adoption of the identities of native birds, of a tawny frogmouth and an owl. These relics evoke a contemporary shamanism, one attuned to the alchemic powers of the human, that can make visible our entanglement with the life and material that surrounds us.

The Museum für Völkerkunde has been closed as it undergoes a complete transformation to reopen as the Weltmuseum (World Museum) in two years time. A key change in curatorial strategy is to contextualise the collection more specifically, to escape the burden of representation by presenting the collection as specifically tied to its origins, describing exactly where, when, and who gathered these objects. Galleries examining histories of colonisation and migration will contextualise our contemporary constitution as a species, yet lacking in the plans is a means of conveying the current dissolution of boundaries and reciprocal make-up of humans, technology, and the natural world.

Through an appropriation of the Museum's equipment and its integration into the display of Jones and Milledge's work, Behavioural Modernity seeks to gesture towards a broadened ethics of care and responsibility in representation.

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